

China's Inter-regional influence through One Belt One Road Foreign Policy

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Abstract

Artikel ini akan membahas mengenai Kebijakan Luar Negeri dari China yaitu Kebijakan One Belt One Road dan bagaimana kebijakan ini berdampak terhadap negara diluar kawasan asia timur. Artikel ini terbagi atas beberapa bagian dimana pengertian akan kebijakan luar negeri dan kebijakan OBOR akan ada di bagian pengantar. Bab 1 dari konten artikel ini akan menjelaskan latar belakang mengapa China mengeluarkan kebijakan luar negeri tersebut. Lalu bab analisis konsep akan menjelaskan kebijakan one belt one road yang akan dikaitkan dengan konsep neoliberalisme, sedangkan bab hasil dan diskusi akan menjelaskan dampak, keuntungan, respons dan tantangan dari kebijakan luar negeri ini terhadap negara di berbagai kawasan diluar asia timur secara global, dan semua itu akan di rangkup menjadi satu dalam bagian terakhir yaitu kesimpulan.

Keywords : *OBOR, China, Foreign Policy, silk route*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout it's history, China has proven itself to be one of the pioneer country not only in the region of East Asia but also globally. The end of the world war 2 resulting into a political coalition view from Mao Zedong and Kuomintang, it's economic reformation through an open door policy and the joining of China in WTO in 2001 had given the perfect opportunity for China to rise itself to the western world and had nourished its relations espescially in economy and trading with countries in different region all over the world and now, what makes China a power to be reckon with, is it's ambition. The one belt one road foreign policy is one of its ambitious plan to establish an integrated and inclusive economy beyond region where China hopes to lead the way through it.

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According to Modelski, a foreign policy is a system of activities that related towards the process of inputs and resulted into an outputs². The actors behind the decision makers usually are government and ministries, though there are various of factors influencing the output of that foreign policy itself which in this case non state actors such as NGO's, society, and interest group can take part in the process of decision making of a foreign policy. Thus, Holsti believe that those factors in the input process ranges from general to specific including the elements of 1. orientations, 2. national roles, 3. objectives, and 4. actions.³

One Belt One Road Foreign policy is a strategy to establish an integrated economy through bilateral partnerships and trades by building a comprehensive network of transportation, including railways, highways, sea ports as well as communications networks and better infrastructure in countries beyond region of Europe, Asia and Africa. It said to be, when its complete will enhance and make it easier for both; host countries and China to do export- import trading and investment that will boost not only the economy growth of china of course, but also the hosting countries. Though it main focus and goal seems to only be economy but it will also have significant diplomatic windfalls. As Premier Li Keqiang commented, “ the OBOR policy was developed not only to boost economic growth, but also to “deepen international cooperation and promote world peace”⁴ through sustained bilateral investment and the economic interdependence it produces. As of now, there are 65 countries from Central Asia, ASEAN, South Asia, Central and Eastern Europe, West Asia, and North Africa that are passed by the OBOR routes.

BACKGROUND : Why China Proposes OBOR Foreign Policy? And would it work?

China of course in several occasions have addressed this foreign policy reasonings was purely benign economic and diplomatic purposes, though many countries have questioned the real motives behind establishing the initiative. Domestically, China view this one belt one road foreign policy to be an insurance in a way to ensure the economy

² Frankel, Joseph, 1963. *The Making of Foreign Policy*. London: Oxford University Press.

³ Holsti, K.J., 1983. *International Politics, A Framework for Analysis*, 4th edition, London: Prentice Hall.

⁴ Bhattacharyya, Anushree (2010) “China's Strategic Advancements in Southeast Asia: Trade Diplomacy and Connectivity”, *Maritime Affairs*, 6(1): pp. 51-70.

growth of China in a long long future , because by having this foreign policy, **First**, it will open access and connects China to many ports and countries beyond barriers that China had not yet have access to. It links sea ports from china to south east asia, Africa and Europe and is seen as a way to increase a better living standards for Chinese people. Why? because the implementation of this foreign policy is by reaching out conducting projects of building transportation and infrastructure especially to those third world countries, and by doing so, **Second**, it indirectly boost China's manufactures to the outside world because it's china products and china people who will build those infrastructure and transportation between the countries. By opening access to strategic markets, in a way it also increase Chinese domestic consumption in import and exports.

Third, it is seen as a way to reduce disparities and economy gap between provinces in china, seeing the central and west province of china is left behind in terms of the economy policies, so by having OBOR policy that directly links not only china to the outside world, but also links each province to China building a great sense of belonging by physically linking west and eastern china and create an understanding of ethnic solidarity that will reduce the possibility of a separatist movement.⁵

How does US responds?

Though domestically china have mentioned reasonings behind this foreign policy, other major countries such as US have different and diverse approach in receiving this foreign policy initiative which are denial and fear. US believe it can't work for certain reason such as that it is only a manipulative way of china taking over the global market and still however benefited other countries, the one who will benefit the most would be china. Another response from US is fear where the Chinese possessed an economy threat in the competition market globally with US, especially in region that China have build projects of infrastructure with, such as in Latin America. Jim Mattis, which is the U.S. Defense Secretary still questions the anomaly and rationale for the OBOR foreign policy on whether or not China may have ulterior motives for making these investments in Asia, Africa and the Middle East⁶, which if it being analysed a little closer, it also became **the**

⁵ Callahan, William A. (2016) "China's "Asia Dream"", *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics*, 1(3): pp. 226-243

⁶https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/monkey-cage/wp/2018/09/11/belt-and-road-projects-direct-chinese-investment-to-all-corners-of-the-globe-what-are-the-local-impacts/?utm_term=.4b7bee08eb8e 10/12/2018 14.41 WIB

anomaly of this issue.

The anomaly of this issues lies on how China would want to invest and fund a massive amount of money in countries so far away from china, even across region that naturally didn't directly benefit china as equally as the amount of what china invested in, especially in countries like Africa and middle east, that not only geographically isn't close but also politically and culturally have little in common and interest with China, which then again sparks the question- what possible reason china have to want to invest and fund many infrastructure and telecommunications projects in countries that's problematic, small and far away from china if its not for gaining support and acceptance from hosting countries in order for this OBOR foreign policy to work?, which at the end will benefit China even more economically. As example in middle east, China had funded countries like the UAE , specifically Abu Dhabi Ports, in its capacity as a regional trading hub, and also has signed a partnership with Cosco, to build new terminals. ⁷While in terms of infrastructure, China funded the railway system in African countries that mostly costs R57.2 billion.

METHODS& CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

China's foreign policy of one belt one road is a suitable example of a current issue that can both be related with concept such as neoliberalism and related to the discussion on the topic of the East Asia Inter-region relationship, because in a way, the core value of the concept of neoliberalism is able to explain the reasonings that might push this particular China's foreign policy initiatives.

According to Campbell, "Neoliberalism is commonly thought of as a political philosophy which prioritize the individual freedom and the right to private property"⁸ it did have the similar core values with liberalism which highly values liberty and individual rights. Though in this case neoliberalism focuses on a different light, which is through an economic approach. To sums up, neoliberalism is an economic system in which highly values individual and private companies role to play a big part in the economy system as

⁷<http://studies.aljazeera.net/en/reports/2017/05/belt-road-vision-future-china-middle-east-relations-170509102227548.html> 10/12/2018 14.45 WIB

⁸ Campbell, John L. and Ove K. Pedersen, eds. (2001): *The Rise of Neoliberalism and Institutional Analysis*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

self-regulating market where states are prevented to intervene in the economy system by limiting the role of states and keep it only as necessary as possible⁹. It promotes for the “free” market to be extended to every part of the public and personal worlds.

Neoliberalism and OBOR Foreign Policy : Tax Customs and Barriers of One Belt One Road Foreign Policy

The foreign policy of one belt one road was basically aiming to establish an integrated and inclusive economy and connectivity between regions of Asia, Europe and Africa, which basically screams the values of neoliberalism behind it. If it is connected, it does make sense to explain the foundation of this china foreign policy was based on values of neoliberalism where both supports the basic idea of reducing barriers to create and further developed an easier access towards economy integration and cooperation. Though the approach are slightly different. In neoliberalism, it is explained free market was conducted easier through the reducing of tax barriers, in which in one belt one road foreign policy, they have a specific tax customs and regulations to be prioritised between host countries and china to avoid tax problems. The tax benefits to be enjoyed by each OBOR country are very much depending on the tax treaty they enter into with China respectively and it goes the same way with the trades through OBOR foreign policy. Example, Sino-Russia Double Taxation Agreement (DTA) where China is very facilitative in lowering the tax rates on royalties from 10% to 6%, and on interests from 10 %to 5%.¹⁰.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

East Asia Inter-regional on OBOR Foreign Policy : How does the EU response?

The foreign policy of one belt one road is a suitable example of how countries in East Asia can influence relations and dynamics outside from the region, in which in this case on how china foreign policy of one belt one road enhance connectivity beyond regions, connecting economy especially Eurasia. The impact and implementation of this foreign policy manage to leave benefits and influence dynamics of other inter-region

⁹ Chomsky, Noam (1999): Profit over People – Neoliberalism and Global Order. New York: Seven Stories Press.

¹⁰ <http://spiegeler.com/chinas-one-belt-one-road-initiative-tax-customs/> 10/12/2018 19.38 WIB

organization, such as in this case European Union.

Though US responds have been filled with fear and doubtful comments regarding china's motives behind one belt one road policy, European countries are more welcoming in regard this idea, considering the The EU is China's largest trading partner, and China is the EU's second largest trade partner after the United States ¹¹thus Jyrki kateinen as the vice president of the European Commission supports the idea of how china and EU can improve connectivity between Europe and Asia, and believe one belt one road foreign policy was one of the path to do it.¹²

¹³Here are the table showcasing the on going and future infrastructure between China and EU

Table 10: Pilot projects considered under the EU-China Connectivity Platform

Country	Proposed project	Country has signed transport-related MoU with China?	Project overlaps with Chinese investment?
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Corridor 5c Highway Project	No	Yes
Bulgaria	Hemus motorway project	Yes	No
Bulgaria	Black Sea motorway project	Yes	No
Bulgaria	Restoration of the design parameters of the Ruse-Varna Railway Line Project	Yes	No
Croatia	Rijeka-Zagreb-Budapest project	Yes	No
Hungary	V0 Rail Cargo Line bypassing Budapest	Yes	No
Hungary	Hungary-Serbia Railway	Yes	Yes
Italy	Genoa Port breakwater project	No	No
Italy	Trieste Integrated Rail Hub	No	No
Latvia	North Sea – Baltic Corridor	Yes	No
Poland	Adjusting Odra River Waterway (E30) to the international waterway standards	Yes	No
Poland	Silesian Channel	Yes	No
Poland	Middle and lower Vistula cascade (E40 and E70 waterways)	Yes	No
Poland	Warszawa-Brzesc connection (E-40 waterway)	Yes	No
Serbia	Projects in the Orient/East-Med Corridor in the Western Balkans Region	Yes	Yes (Partially)
Slovakia	Košice Intermodal Terminal	No	No
Slovakia	Leopoldov Intermodal Terminal	No	No
Slovakia	Bratislava Trimodal Terminal	No	No
Slovenia	Railroad Project from Koper to Divača	No	No

Source: Outcomes of the "First Working Group Meeting of the EU – China Connectivity Platform" (Brussels, Belgium, 20-22 January 2016), and the "Second Chairs' Meeting of EU – China Connectivity Platform" (Brussels, Belgium, 1 June 2017)

As a prove aside from the table, 11 EU member states government have signed the OBOR cooperation with China and ongoing now is the China-Europe express freight

¹¹ Dent, Christopher M., 1999, "The European Union and East Asia: An economic relationship", London: Routledge

¹² <http://www.euexperts.eu/blog/one-belt-one-road-initiative-really-mean/> 11/12/2018 09.06 WIB

¹³ <http://www.gmfus.org/publications/europes-response-belt-and-road-initiative> 11/12/2018 09.11 WIB

trains that are busy traveling across the Eurasian. In 2017, there are 3,673 trips that were made, going up more than 100% into 116% from 2016 and exceeding the total number combined during the past six years.¹⁴ The train services reach 36 European cities in 13 countries and able to ease the access in Chinese markets of European goods.¹⁵

What Benefits the EU get?

First, OBOR act as a benchmark that ease the access of markets of Eurasia so it's an opportunity for Europe to build a greater Eurasian market. **Second**, it's a way to integrate sense of belonging and build a stronger nation within the EU, since OBOR pathway connects countries of EU considering many disintegration and ethnic issues revolving EU such as Brexit, Russia-Ukraine crisis. **Third**, it gives Europe a chance to enhance its influence across border towards region such as Asia Pacific in terms of interest and international affairs.

Response from other region : Does **developing countries** benefits equally from OBOR compared to China?

It is without a doubt the aims of OBOR initiative; an easier access towards global economy market through better infrastructure and funded constructions of projects seems tempting to developing countries, especially those who are not in the stable financial or political condition to achieve those. OBOR did benefit developing countries that host and support OBOR itself, because it is an opportunity for them to improve their infrastructure condition and strengthen the private sectors in many countries, which is very much beneficial to those countries who rely mainly on natural resources but don't have the infrastructure or technology to equip that, which in this case enables to enhance further innovations towards economy that doesn't heavily depend on natural resources but varies to technology and manufactures.

¹⁴ "China and Europe can work together on the Belt and Road Initiative", [H.E. Ambassador Zhang Ming](https://www.euractiv.com/section/economy-jobs/opinion/china-and-europe-can-work-together-on-the-belt-and-road-initiative/), accessed through <https://www.euractiv.com/section/economy-jobs/opinion/china-and-europe-can-work-together-on-the-belt-and-road-initiative/> 11/12/2018 08.37 WIB

¹⁵ *ibid*

Africa

China has invested \$14 billion in Eastern Africa Kenya's Standard Gauge Railway (SGR) which is a 485km single-track railroad that connects Mombasa to Kenyan capital, Nairobi¹⁶ and extended to many other cities and countries in Africa, which also facilitates routes for trade between China and Africa

Middle East

China Machinery Engineering Corporation funded and assisted a hydropower station in Pakistan named the Nehru Tim Jielu Mu Hydropower Station which also is the largest hydropower project in Pakistan¹⁷. It provides electricity via hydroelectric generation, considering electricity is a big problem in Pakistan that during summer, power was constantly cut off.

South East Asia

Brunei has massive oil and gas resources, but their lack of material in producing oil and the low equipped gas pipelines has proven to become a problem in which china find its way to help by providing millions in loans and funding a steel pipe called huludao city steel pipe industrial that not only produces more than 100.000 tons of oil and gas pipelines and benefited brunei around \$100 million but manage to provide brunei people 300 job opportunities¹⁸

However, though developing countries benefits also from this foreign policy, still China benefits from both the financing and construction of infrastructure projects, while the hosting countries must bear the financial risk. When trade volumes are high the arrangement will be mutually beneficial, and that may not matter, but when it is not, it could become a source of concern for the recipient country

Challenges and Barriers of One Belt One Road Foreign policy

European countries felt an unequal level playing field because how Chinese companies conduct dumping. Dumping is when a company in a country sell a product at much lower price to be exported in foreign companies in foreign countries if it compared

¹⁶ <https://borgenproject.org/one-belt-one-road-benefits/> 11/12/2018 11.27 WIB

¹⁷ <http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/internationaldevelopment/2017/01/30/the-impact-of-chinas-one-belt-one-road-initiative-on-developing-countries/> 11/12/2018 11.30 WIB

¹⁸ *Ibid*

to the price that they sell in their own country¹⁹. This creates an unbalance level of demand for the export products from china in the foreign companies, since dumping consequences makes Chinese products very cheap, so in a way it disadvantages local companies in foreign country because it can't compete with that low of a price for a product.

The lack of reciprocity comes due to a lot of restrictions and terms of conditions of FDI that comes to China while Chinese investment are flowing easily and free in Europe. Taking note of China's history and values of how state control and dominate most of the important stuffs in china, up until now it includes the flow of information and foreign investment and companies, specifically in this case from European countries and companies that are met with a lot of demands if it want to invest in china²⁰

Third, related to the dumping activity done by china, logically companies who conduct dumping benefited at a much lower level since they sell the product to foreign companies much cheaper as well. Though in china, companies like those are still benefited a lot since despite they are private companies, the ownership of the companies are still somehow controlled by the state in which the state subsidized money and give financial advise to the private companies, which eventually creates an unequal level playing field between private companies in different countries.

In ASEAN, many developing countries receive great benefit out of this foreign policy though still risks existed such as foreign exchange volatility; risk of recession; price instability; 'crowding-out' of private sector investment; legal and regulatory issues; dearth of pre-existing basic infrastructure; corruption; bureaucratic issues; and poor transparency.²¹

Political system and stability of the hosting countries has also become a challenge for China to conduct its foreign policy, especially countries with strong governance among the routes such India, Indonesia, and Vietnam which will not likely to accept large numbers of Chinese workers or take on high levels of debt knowing the possibility their local companies incompetence among Chinese investments, products and workers.

¹⁹ Crossick, Stanley, 2006, "The rise of China and Its Implications for the EU", East Asian Institute at National university of Singapore, *EAI Working Papers*, No. 132

²⁰ John Farnell and Paul Irwin, 2016, "*The Politics of EU – China Economic Relations : An Uneasy Partnership*", New York : Palgrave Macmillan

²¹ <http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/internationaldevelopment/2017/01/30/the-impact-of-chinas-one-belt-one-road-initiative-on-developing-countries/> 11/12/2018 11.33 WIB

Instability of ethno-religious conflict that happened in a country is an influential factors as well. China couldn't invest or conduct projects of OBOR if the middle of a civil war in a foreign country. It is hardly a promising market for Chinese goods.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, China's foreign policy of One Belt One Road has such a diverse responses from countries all over the region and manage to influence dynamics of other region beyond east asia. Some deny it will work, some fear China has motives behind it, some welcomes it with open arms to enhance connectivity even more, some welcomes it hesitantly, fearing the financial risks if the trade volumes didn't constantly go up. Though it can be guaranteed every country among the route of one belt one road policy will be benefited out of this foreign policy, China will still, benefits the most out of it. Despite the tempting benefits, though risks and challenges still existed as mentioned above. Thus, China needs to really increase its transparency, maintain to constantly reach out to the third world countries to get their support and approval and emphasize it's friendly purposes behind this foreign policy.

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